

Development of NMC cathode powder with core/shell morphology for long cycle life LIB batteries

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NMC ($\text{LiNi}_x\text{Mn}_y\text{Co}_z\text{O}_2$) cathode materials with a nickel content exceeding 80%, exhibit a remarkable discharge capacity of 200 mAh/g at 4.3 V [1]. However, increasing Ni content can involve rapid capacity fading, short cycle life, and poor thermal/structural stability. These drawbacks stem from the increased reactivity of Ni with surface oxygen during charge-discharge cycles, as well as larger Li/Ni cationic mixing, which can deteriorate the electrochemical performance. In order to overcome these issues, different approaches to develop NMC materials with controlled core/shell structured morphology have been proposed [2]. For instance, high Ni content ensures high energy density and increased storage capacity, while Mn-rich shell provides the improved structural and thermal stability. In this work, NMC90 (Ni:Co:Mn = 9:0.5:0.5), NMC622 (Ni:Co:Mn = 6:2:2) and cathode powders having Ni-rich Core/Mn-rich Shell have been synthesized via facile process-controlled oxalate-assisted co-precipitation method by optimization of process parameters under steady performance tests. The formation of core and shell structured particles having two different

compositions (i.e. NMC90 core and NMC622 shell) has been achieved via a two-staged synthesis approach. The microstructural analysis techniques including SEM, EDX and XRD have been used to study the compositional, morphological and structural properties of the synthesized powders.

The first five cycles of charge-discharge performance of the synthesized NMC powders as cathode materials are conducted at a rate of C/10 in the potential range of 2.7 V to 4.2 V (Figure 1). GCD tests are carried out on half-cell form fabricated with metallic lithium (Li) as anode and Glass Fiber-separators. NMC 90, NMC 622 and NMC core/shell delivers a first discharge capacity of ~37 mAh/g, ~6.5 mAh/g and 131 mAh/g at C/10, showing stable performance over five cycles, while NMC 622 experiences a capacity loss with each subsequent cycle. First charge capacity is higher than first discharge capacity, indicating partial Li-ion loss during cycling. This core/shell cathode powder with NMC 90 as core and NMC 622 as shell provides a promising cathode material for Li-ion Batteries.

Figure 1. Charge/discharge voltage curve as a function of specific capacity of NMC90, NMC 622 and core/shell structured NMC powders.

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References

- [1] Noh, H.-J.; Youn, S.; Yoon, C.S.; Sun, Y.-K. Comparison of the structural and electrochemical properties of layered $\text{Li}[\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_y\text{Mn}_z]\text{O}_2$ ($x = 1/3, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8$ and 0.85) cathode material for lithium-ion batteries. *Journal of Power Sources* 2013, 233, 121-130.
- [2] Chen, Z.; Zhang, L.; Wu, X.; Song, K.; Ren, B.; Li, T.; Zhang, S. Effect of N/P ratios on the performance of $\text{LiNi}_{0.8}\text{Co}_{0.15}\text{Al}_{0.05}\text{O}_2\|\text{SiO}_x/\text{Graphite}$ lithium-ion batteries. *Journal of Power Sources* 2019, 439: 227056.

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